

**CHALLENGES TO OPEN
SCIENCE SCHOOLING INNOVATION
AND RE-THINKING SCIENCE EDUCATION**
Policy paper

WwEU

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This Family Based policy paper is based on 2 years of practical experimentation with the participation of five secondary schools, teachers and students, two knowledge partners and one quality assurance partner from different European countries.

The aim of this paper is to summarize the lessons learned in the field of family-based open science schooling from the project and similar projects referring to practical experience to inform and direct future Erasmus+ and European priorities.

The lessons learned are based on dialogues with the project's students, teachers and families along the project, observation based on direct participation in project processes, analysis of the process outcomes from all project scenario and a questionnaire specially created to catch concrete testimonies. Key messages, unedited and authentic, from teachers and students are inserted.

The language of this paper is not academic, making its content accessible and attractive to very large audiences.

The text also identifies the most important challenges including the community in general in the realisation of open science schooling and will recommend focuses and priorities in the 2021-27 Erasmus+ programme directly addressing those challenges.

In other words, the text wishes to contribute to an understanding of what further steps should be taken in the core field addressed.

Thus, the text might inspire new European initiatives based on and going further than the project.

Rich examples of the project experience can be found in the project [website](#)

The FAMILY BASED OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING project 2019-21 is funded by the European Commission Erasmus+ program

INTRODUCING THE PROJECT

In 2015, the international community signed the Agenda for Sustainable Development 2030 and set 17 bold goals to reach a better and equal society. The fourth goal was established to be Quality Education, aiming to “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all” (UNESCO, 2017).

In our current society, in which digitalization and technologies transverse almost (if not all) dimensions of our everyday life, Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Maths (STEAM) abilities and digital competences become key factors for students to reach a good life. This scenario calls for a change in the school education paradigm.

It is one of the highest priorities in the European Commission and the OECD as well as leading research communities to work on one of the biggest challenges to 21st century education, and this is to engage and re-engage young student along their teenage years in science learning.

Family Based OSS project aimed to contribute to the Science Learning Innovation Agenda through practical experimentation in secondary school, and guided by Commission recommendation and by guidelines from leading science learning research communities.

From this project, it was expected that students engaged in real-life science in open collaborating community and family teams, could create new images of what applied science is and how it can be practiced among teenagers.

At the same time, this open schooling environment should provide a reliable context for building responsible science mindsets toward active citizenship.

Thus, the project focused on and work through 3 main objectives:

- Encouraging families to become real partners in school life and activities through participatory design

- Cocreating ‘science everywhere’ activities alongside teachers, students and families to support responsible science education

- Supporting the deployment of immersive Joint Science Missions involving the community as a whole so that schools become agents of community

The project consortium was organized accordingly: five secondary schools as practice partners, two academic institutions as knowledge partners and a quality assurance partner.

The consortium mission was to develop practically useful guidance to secondary schools and science teachers on how to organize and facilitate family based open science schooling with good quality, based on the practical experimentation along the project and on co-creation with the students and their families.

The mission of this paper is to transform this experience and knowledge into policy recommendation.

The project innovation is therefore linked to the European re-thinking science education agenda, dedicated to find brand new ways to make science and science learning attractive to young students, precisely along the years in which they strongly build their identity, personality and professional intents.

PART 1 – THE FRAME

The European science learning innovation agenda

In order to motivate more young people to engage in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) related careers, initiatives across Europe started to link science education more closely with the arts and other subjects, using inquiry-based pedagogy, and engaging with a wide range of societal actors and industries.

*RECOMMENDATION on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning
Council of the European Union 2018*

The European Commission, leading research communities and policy-makers are calling for dramatic innovation in all forms of science learning and at all educational levels. Re-thinking (science) education, and open science schooling is one of the educational changes increasingly recommended by them.

This is because the 21st century students create resistance towards science, science education, and a life in science, based on negative images of science built up in secondary school.

The result of this is Europe losing most of its young potential science and innovation talent, which is unaffordable in times of serious challenges to life on earth and human welfare.

But the problem is not the young students.

The problem is science, science education and science in society.

The science learning innovation takes place in a strange landscape with many extremes: on one hand it seems that science teaching is the most conservative, restrictive and traditional of all school subjects; on the other hand, the surrounding community and world offer thousands of dynamic and exciting science cases and missions.

The problem is the giant gap between these two extremes in the science education scenario.

The project, together with other European initiatives, has been carrying out experimentations on what science learning innovation and open science schooling means and how such innovation can be implemented in secondary schools.

Family Based has called this knowledge and experience “bank and accompanying innovation strategies” to *The European science learning innovation agenda*. The project forms part of this agenda and set out to contribute to the development of innovative and science learning and science experience.

Along its life, the project has been referring to state of the art critical science learning research as well as to the European Commission’s very clear science learning innovation recommendations and guidance.

Open Science Schooling: the re-thinking science education way

Encourage “open schooling” where schools, in cooperation with other stakeholders, become an agent of community well-being; FAMILIES ARE ENCOURAGED TO BECOME REAL PARTNERS IN SCHOOL LIFE AND ACTIVITIES; professionals from enterprise, civil and wider society are actively involved in bringing real-life projects into the classroom.

COMMISSION 2015, SCIENCE EDUCATION FOR RESPONSIBLE CITIZENSHIP

When confronted with the challenge to create interest in innovation among the young students, most schools and teachers (and students!!) react in what we might call the “way of modernisation”.

This way is about adding “modern” activities to traditional education in the classroom.

In the last years many attempts to “modernize” science teaching have been carried out.

Such “modernizations” might be visits to science resources outside the school, punctual engagement in science activities in the community, new work forms in the class or participation in various forms of science competitions.

A popular “modernization” is to use new technology and even digital games.

But, punctual, stand-alone, superficial, alibi or entertainment-based activities will not have “serious and lasting impact on the young learners, their identity formation and their life prospects”.

The traditional “visiting” activities will not do the job.

Why?

Because such activities are add-ons to traditional classroom teaching, and:

- they do not basically aim to change classroom teaching
- they do not create genuine open schooling
- they do not create lasting and sustainable innovation interest in the students
- and very important, they do not succeed in becoming a part of the young student’s identity, mentality and behaviour.

The European Commission is asking **to re-think** the fundamentals of science education and **to develop** new ways of engaging young people in science.

The short version of this complex re-thinking is that it is not enough to “modernize” traditional science education, or to add new features such as project work.

The new generations of students and the new and constantly changing global reality call for fundamental re-thinking of what science education is and should be, this means: re-thinking the very basic axioms and the very discourse of traditional science education.

To accomplish this radical and urgent mission, the Commission invites to experiment with open science schooling.

In fact, the Commission is asking for a **new learning culture**.

Educational authorities and schools should make strong efforts to build a new learning culture for teachers and in particular for students.

And that has been the intention of this project, to develop a realistic and implementable Model of Open Science Schooling to contribute to this new learning culture.

PART 2 - THE SCHOOLS

Secondary schools jumping from traditional education to open schooling

TEACHERS

Teachers need to have created a professional learning community that meets regularly, is interested in professional development, is supported by the management, and the additional effort the teachers make is acknowledged

Important to be aware of the lack of time, lack of recognition, lack of clear connection between academic curriculum and OSS challenges, many teachers see this as additional' to school work

Short but repetitive meetings can be organized both for teachers and students. Content can be successful scientists, their contribution, their popularity in the community and the happiness in their eyes

Teachers should read up on the newest science journals and ideas therein, be well-educated on each topic they present to their students and make quick science-based quizzes or reviews ("digests which could take up to 15 minutes) discussing hot topics before the beginning each lesson

The main principles of innovation in secondary schools should rely on the notion of passive engagement because it inspires the idea that students should have almost complete freedom of thought, ideas and expression when it comes to the inter-(and-self-) distribution of new science ideas

As in open-science-schooling in general, the most important hurdles are environmental limitations, the window of time students have to adapt to new forms of schooling and the question of how open younger students and older teachers are to new ideas

Students mostly focus on the short period benefits. It requires effort to tell them the long-term profits

STUDENTS

In the project, students did what they were expected to do but they needed more personalized feedback about how they were doing. Co-creation happened during the second year when students and families were given the freedom to create their inquiry paths – our students were older than the other ones, so the initial missions were a bit childish (they said). They said they had studied those phenomena in their previous schools so they saw some of the first science at home missions disconnected from the curriculum. During the second cycle, they enjoyed the community missions much more

They would organize projects and competitions to increase their interest in science and teachers should provide the necessary opportunities for them to participate in these competitions.

Students like international schooling ideas. Clubs and scientific groups would help them research important science topics better

The students think there are many challenges in adapting to new forms of schooling, but they have managed with their tasks just fine and will continue to do so regardless of the difficulties they come across

All students agreed that science at home missions is not so easily community missions – very easily, all said. They should be done as group projects with families expected as contributors and the template for reporting should include space for parents to write their names as such

The most important principles in creating science interest and capacity among young students and a lasting and sustainable impact on them

TEACHERS

Relevant tasks according to age; connection to the curriculum; parents 'involvement at an early stage - it is clear parents help with projects in primary school, one parent said, why should we be anonymous, does this not encourage plagiarism at a later stage.

Students should be part and parcel of schooling, not disconnected from it; governing bodies should extend the existing curricula to integrate end-of-term and end-of-year

research projects whose purpose is to collect data that is likely to solve a real problem and present a solution – could be in the form of campaign, social experiment, community service

Students have to have integrity in their work and know exactly how real scientists do their job as well as how young people may contribute

Science has become a core issue with the advent of climate change and covid-19. To ensure the students' involvement, any form of scientific engagement should be necessary, mainly in the process of their general schooling. To motivate them, external involvement through partnerships or parent supervision are some nice ideas to try

Encouragement should be in every single activity. It should show them the relevance of that specific activity in daily life or popular subjects such as electric cars, health, global warming, etc.

Intriguing activities can increase their curiosity

We must make sure that families, students and other teachers in schools see the benefit of activities. This will make it sustainable

STUDENTS

Relevance according to age; connection to the science curriculum at school

One student said: community activities will be always interesting to young students because young students are curious by default. The problem is when this curiosity is killed in school with too theoretical teaching. If teaching in the classroom is complemented by meaningful practical research/inquiry tasks in the community, missions could build on them as end-of-year assignments – this will build community spirit in the long run

The students agree that they should stick to the scientific process and beware of spreading misinformation

To the students, international ideas and open-science schooling is a good starting point and sturdy guideline moving forward in their educational work

Missions should be joyful

Online simultaneous experiments can be done with student

Teachers should have access to authentic tasks, by creating links to the local community (business, local authorities, third sector) to identify and get access to real life tasks that the teachers can use.

Budapest Agenda: Enabling Teachers for Entrepreneurship Education

When discussing innovation in science education and re-engaging and motivating young students in science, this innovation clearly goes in the direction of open schooling.

We know that works.

BUT if it works...

Why is so difficult to jump from traditional education to open science schooling?

Because we don't know how to implement the model within the restricted reality of European education, in fact, in many schools the real innovation is not even possible; and because schools and teachers and students need to create such capacity through stepwise dismantling the traditional forms of education.

A spiral of learning and experience is needed to create real change. A single jump will never do the job.

A unanimous European policy and research community strongly recommends using co-driving and co-creation as basic principles when fostering innovation interest, skills and capacity, also in early schooling.

In practice this means that the young people will need to create innovation interest, skills and capacity through real-life and real-time and practical projects, not through classroom instruction and theoretical exercises.

However, the same is true for the young teachers: also, they will need to create didactic competence in the field of fostering innovation mentality, and they will do this through practical projects working side-by-side with the young people.

Practical experimentation in many schools from across Europe clearly evidence that no teachers are prepared to work in innovation missions or in open schooling model!

The teachers engaging in such practices are front-runners and pioneers, dedicated to bringing about change in school education.

They struggle to make this happen, and sometimes they need to step back: the obstacles are difficult to overcome and the workload too demanding.

Traditionally, secondary schools are responsible for education in classes, tests and exams, not engaging in any form of community activity or community innovation. They are increasingly top-down controlled by educational authorities, in general, teachers are under pressure - tests, competition, funding based on student grades, evaluation of teacher performance, etc.

Therefore, most teachers, do not wish to engage in innovation, or they might wish to, but do not have the support or the needed resources.
Most European schools do not have the needed room to move, their hands are tied, and that does not make life easier for pioneers' teachers.

When they manage to engage in for example a European project based on open science schooling like Family Based, they mostly have to manage everything themselves, and often without additional resources from the school.
We call these teachers the "heroes of experimentation".
They want to change; they want to do good for the students.
But after a few years on their own, many of them burn out and give up.
The lack of serious support from the school and from the educational system usually allows these teachers a limited number of years in the project world.

And you might say, but the students, at least, are openly interested in innovation, right?

Wrong.

The classroom mentality is also and sometimes very much shared by the students! They are used to being told what to do, how to do it and when to do it.
They are excited about the new project initiatives, but they are still positioned in the old educational mentality. There is very little space for improvisation because they are not used, what they are used is to follow instructions.

In all the projects in which we have worked on the open science schooling model, we can see an interesting experience: if the students get too much innovation, they start to ask the teacher what this is all about.

What does it mean?

It means that the classroom mentality is in the blood of all the players.

But the times we live in are challenging and changing very fast, that's why the Commission is calling for changes and calling them an "urgent mission".
The young generations cannot wait. They need to develop the 21st century skills and capacity they will need in their further education and in their professional and personal lives.
The 21st-century innovation is expected to be driven by citizens, all sorts of community resources and by any stakeholder in the community able to and willing to change things.

Of course, this is not obvious if we think about the traditional school model.

HOW can schools start to work on changing? Each school will find its own way, but there are certain general approaches, here are some advices.:

STRATEGIC APPROACH

Schools wishing to engage in such roles as drivers of change and innovation are strongly recommended to apply a strategic approach: careful discussions and preparations are needed, and in particular it is important to build on strong consensus among management and teachers, as well as create serious dialogues with potential community alliances.

BOTTOM UP

It is also of the utmost importance not to create top-down initiatives through organisational agreements between leaders and managers in the community resources: ecosystems.

The extended roles in the community of the school should build on the students' open science schooling engagement and take this engagement to a higher level.

This bottom-up approach will ensure that the school's engagement is continuously focused on the students' learning and co-driving.

STUDENTS' CO-DRIVING

The ultimate aim of the school's new roles is to offer students' relevant 21st century learning opportunities. To maintain this aim students should always be at the centre of the school's engagement, as co-drivers of the innovation missions.

The school should not attempt to replace the students' engagement, on the contrary: the new roles of the school should increase the quality of the students' learning and allow more and more students to engage in and benefit from open science schooling.

CREATING ALLIANCES

One of the prominent new roles of the school, in support of the students' innovation science missions and innovation learning, should precisely be to continuously build new permanent alliances with institutions, resources and citizens in the community, this means a continuous ecosystem building process. In this way the school will allow the students to benefit from a still growing ecosystem of collaboration in the community and will allow the community to benefit from a systematic and sustained engagement of the students and the school.

SHARING THE STORIES

The school should take advantage of its new roles and of the students' innovation science missions: it should systematically share the stories with all relevant resources in the community and describe the benefit of the engagement for students and for the community and its citizens. Visibility is key...

Evidently, the students must be deeply engaged in this sharing, including through the social networks.

EXPLOIT FUNDING

In case the school is willing to take on such new ecosystems, the school will inevitably become a *pioneer school*. This means that the school can apply for a variety of funding – from local and national funds to the European programmes.

This is a great way to create more economy for the activities and to share the new experience in wider circles

OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING MAINSTREAMED

Most schools will start its new pioneer journey through engaging a few student teams in such innovation science missions.

It is important for the school to build further engagement on this practical experience.

However, as soon as the school wishes to extend the science missions to more students and to widen considerably the number of students engaged in such open science schooling learning, it will be necessary for the school to take the approach to a higher level: precisely to a "school as organisation" level.

It is at this point the school will benefit from engaging as driver of change in the community, as this would be the best framework for engaging more and more students in innovation learning.

Mainstreaming open science schooling for innovation learning might precisely happen through the systematic engagement in community innovation of the school as organisation.

Now, ask yourself this question: is there room in your school for such “working though”?

And,

Can open science schooling be integrated in the science curricula, which are the most important challenges for secondary schools engaging in such new didactics?

TEACHERS

As end-of-term/school projects assigned by teachers of science and co-created by students with their families. These should weigh towards the students’ marks to motivate students (grading is motivational but the criteria and rubrics should be set in advance and should include more than academic achievement such as team spirit, innovation, the potential for making a difference, etc).

It is important to prepare a well-organized schedule according to the school curricula. Matching activities with ongoing lessons would enhance the concentration of students and so their success

Optional clubs and extra-curricular groups based largely in science as well as the implementation of science-based schooling into the main body of lessons are generally good ideas

A well-organized schedule can be prepared according to the school curricula. Matching activities with ongoing lessons would enhance the concentration of students and so their success

Most important, it’s an education that creates adults – future citizens – who already have experience, from their education, in finding and implementing real solutions to real problems. This is something that our current education not only does not do, but doesn’t even try to do.

Marc Prensky, “Education to Better their World – Unleashing the power of 21st century kids”, 2016

We know that the European Commission calls for powerful innovation of science learning in schools, and for educational players to contribute to experimentation that creates good practice and useful knowledge.

The Commission in particular invites experimentation based on the open science schooling approach: schools opening the doors to the community and engaging students in real-life science challenges.

Open science schooling innovation engagement should not be a new subject in the curriculum, says the Commission, nor should it be a series of punctual events across the school year.

However, lessons learned from several Erasmus+ projects tell us that for many secondary schools developing open science schooling appears overwhelming and complicated and often conflicts with increasingly overcrowded curricula. The school curricula are increasingly overloaded in most European schools and leave very little space for alternative and innovative learning activities. Without forgetting that most European governments are more interested in the average national test scores than in the young students' learning. This makes most schools hesitate to engage in such science learning innovation.

The reality leads us to a conclusion: what is needed are open science schooling approaches that appear realistic to the schools and the science teachers and can be easily integrated either into the science curricula or in alternative practice carried out in parallel to the science curricula.

Many years of experimenting with the Open Schooling model, show us that there are 3 basic principles for schools willing to integrate open science schooling into the curricula:

- the open science schooling must be extremely attractive to young students and engage them deeply and critically in real-life science activities and most importantly offer them new images of what science is and could be for them
- the open science schooling must be realistic and implementable in average secondary schools, and without revolutionizing the entire curriculum
- the open science schooling must be carried out in close interaction with science resources in the local and virtual communities

And there are 3 different levels for schools on how to do it:

✓ Changing school curricula

Schools, teachers and students should continuously put pressure on educational authorities at all levels to change school curricula with the aim to reserve considerable time in the weekly schedules for non-subject defined and test-free activities.

Such non-subject defined and test-free activities might precisely be used for innovation science missions, entrepreneurial engagement – or similar forms of experimentation equipping the young students with 21st century skills.

For example, public authorities in future-oriented community, regions or countries might decide that one day a week is reserved for such experimentation, and that

the school will be open after normal school hours to continued student engagement

✓ Integrating in school curricula

Until dedicated time and space is reserved for such experimentation, the missions need, at least partly, to be integrated in the school curricula.

Teachers dedicated to work with the students in innovation science missions are constantly negotiating such curricula integration with the school management and with the other teachers.

First of all, teachers engaged in innovation missions need the full support of the school management, and the school management should help negotiate flexible integration of the missions in the weekly schedules.

What we have learned from other Erasmus+ initiatives is that there are different ways to integrate science innovation in the curricula:

- in some schools a few weekly hours are reserved for various forms of “open activities”
- sometimes a teacher decides to devote an entire subject-semester to the innovation missions; the teacher will try to link the missions to that subject
- sometimes a team of teachers of different subjects agree to jointly create the time needed for the innovation; the team of teachers will try to integrate the subjects into the innovation missions

In most cases the involved teachers need to combine various options to ensure the needed time for the innovation missions.

However, no matter how flexibly the missions are integrated in the curricula over a certain period, the students (and sometimes also the teachers) need to add “personal time” to work in the missions.

✓ Creating a new learning culture that allows young students to drive innovation beyond school curricula and school schedules

Remember that the Commission knows all this. This is why the Commission encourage “rule-breakers”; in the sense of schools and teachers experimenting with new didactics even if the education system is not moving. And this is why the Commission is asking for a **new learning culture**.

To conclude this chapter and linked to the new learning culture that the Commission requests, we are giving some ideas on measures/steps that Open science schooling cultures might include:

- use possible free time and space in the curricula systematically
- allow student teams to pursue their interest and dedication after school hours, and by provide resources to the young teams at the school after school hours (open workshops)
- allow students to continue and deepen their science mission engagement in weekends and to some extent during long school holidays and provide basic resources to the young teams at the school after school hours (open workshops)
- encourage student teams to deploy their science missions’ work to the community in collaboration with key mission resources
- encourage the students to involve family and friends

- exploit their virtual social and gaming networks to the max, including involving peers from other countries in the missions

Schools should make constant efforts to stepwise establish such open science schooling cultures in spite of existing curricula.

A special and very important perspective

We know it is not easy for teachers in secondary schools to learn to work in open schooling activities, and no teachers have been trained to work with the new 21st century competences: innovation capacity, entrepreneurial mentality and learning in real-life communities.

Some teachers will successfully be able to work their way through these dramatic changes, but many teachers will not.

This is why it is of **paramount importance** to train the new generation of teachers to work in such open schooling settings, including to get used to the new teacher roles.

This points towards dramatic change and innovation in the European teacher educations: the new generation of young teachers needs to acquire the new teacher competences during their initial teacher education, including getting practical experience in various forms of open schooling didactics.

PART 3 - THE COMMUNITY

The community and family members willing to be co-responsible for re-engaging young students in science learning and a life in science

TEACHERS

Schools need to set themselves a goal, find the potential partners, contact them, arrange a meeting, clearly present their needs, ask for support and take advantage of this support by completing the tasks set and presenting the results to the community partners, acknowledging their contribution. In our community sessions we contacted the young mayor, the representatives in the city council, parents who are doctors, former students who were willing to support our missions

Direct contact with resources mostly works, however it is always better to contact via a reference. This breaks the boundaries rapidly and speeds up the process.

So, it is better to have a reference to save time.

Community resources related to health and safety are the most important ones

Students can help spread knowledge through announcements, presentations and debates in their local community. They can also travel across their nation to spread their ideas, as well as visit museums to enrich their knowledge

It creates a significant encouragement on students. Families and teacher should be always in contact via WhatsApp groups. Feedback should be continuous from both sides

Parents are too busy oftentimes, but the fact that they say yes to child taking part in activities is sometimes enough.

Older students have no expectations for parents to actively participate, they are independent enough to cope by themselves(teenagers)

When students are young, they see parents as role models; parents can create an atmosphere that feeds the child's curiosity or else see that free time could be spent on the sofa, in front of the TV with chips and a game console, etc. When parents support school activities children see value in school, trust their teachers more and they are more motivated to learn

We imagine parents as people who sign off their participation with their names, are acknowledged and are not behind the scenes, for example, they should not be invited ONLY to parents' meetings/teacher-parent conferences where they passively listen to what the teacher says. They should be part of all major activities of the school with formal invitations sent to them; through informal meetings to discuss conflicting situations. Schools should treat them as partners – not easy but the more each party gets to know the other one, the less the prejudice/bias (because perceptions can be negative sometimes)

Schools should create positive learning environments – when we do not do our job well at school, students suffer, parents become hostile; when we do it well, parents are ready to support us in any way. This positive climate is a prerequisite for the subsequent meaningful projects/missions we do together

Parents and family involvement does well to facilitate scientific work, be it in groups or individual, and encourage the students to finish their tasks in due time and hone their skills and knowledge in science. It's a healthy form of motivation for the main body of students

The families are more than willing to participate in their children's work, especially of international caliber. They like the idea of a change in the school's usual curricula and are as open as the students are to innovation and scientific progress

The parents could attend the students' presentations, provide funding, help meet quotas or criteria and serve as an actively motivating factor for the students without excessive pressure

Family based science activities should be involved in all lessons. However, details and time limits should be well thought, studied and organised

Scientific explanations about the benefits of family-student communication should be told them. Some examples can be given

FAMILIES

Some parents prefer to separate school from the family – they are skeptics of OSS/family-based; others were open to what will come out of this participation and they were surprised that some of the missions were better than they'd expected – fun time with kids, quality time with all the members, closer relationships with kids

One mother said: parents should not be anonymous when they help kids with project work

The families welcome the idea of their own involvement in schooling, because they want to be an active part of their school's community and see how their children as well as the younger generations in general are doing - in other words, they want to stay up-to-date on current issues

It makes student happy and successful. Schools should organise such meetings with the help of professionals. Especially a meeting with teacher from another country would be great. It can be online or preferably face to face

STUDENTS

Students relied on the parents and teachers to establish the links

Students like the idea of family involvement, because it adds to their motivation. The ones whose parents aren't available usually involve other relatives, or anybody who's willing to participate, so the main issue in this involvement basically solves itself

We see parents as supporters and teachers

Teenagers do not want their parents to be involved, maybe younger students would be happy to work together with their families

The students like the parents' involvement so long as it doesn't become overly strict, because that would hinder their motivational progress in lessons

The students tend to think non-materialistically, so as long as their parents are simply remotely involved, but don't get mixed up in their science missions too much, they are more than glad to welcome them. This means they don't want their parents to get over-involved

Outcomes of family-based activities should be used in marking system and some exams should be eliminated

In order to achieve a strong Home School Collaboration and partnership, teachers need to be capable of establishing and maintaining good communication channels with family members. Furthermore, objective from the fourth sustainable development goal consists of increasing the supply of qualified teachers, including through international cooperation, that are able to meet and support students to face future social and environmental challenges in their adult life
UNESCO, 2017

In the limited version open science schooling is about students' and student teams' learning through interaction with the community and real-life challenges in the community. In the extended version open science schooling is about the engagement of the school as organisation in community challenges.

The vision is that most of the science learning is expected to take place outside the classrooms and schools and is strongly linked to real-life science activities, supplemented by "learning on demand and when needed".

One thing is sure: the more "real" and "serious" the students' engagement, the better the students' learning and the more benefit for the community!

In the Family Based "community" was understood in its widest sense: local physical community, the region, science communities, and virtual communities supplemented by virtual resources. The idea is that there are no "right or wrong" communities.

The globalised world and the 21st century students do not separate these worlds in the way the present educational systems do.

They work with the physical and virtual communities as one world and local science engagement might very well include considerable virtual social networking.

The roles of the community are many and important in open science schooling scenarios and experimentation.

Therefore, the project invited the students and teachers to work in different forms of communities along their science missions. A number of people and institutions from various forms of physical and virtual communities were invited to be involved through the missions.

From the project experience, we can see that open science schooling is still in its first stages in some schools, and even more so in the collaborating communities. Science resources in the community are not at all used to collaborate with young students along considerable periods, and not at all used to integrate student teams in their research and innovation circles.

The science communities and their professionals can only develop such collaborative competences through continued practice.

Once the science communities are mobilised to work with open science schooling, the community will be able to deliver important resources to the schools and to the teachers.

Early science learning will become a collective mission, not simply a school responsibility.

As a teacher said: Schools should create positive learning environments – when we do not do our job well at school, students suffer, parents become hostile; when we do it well, parents are ready to support us in any way. This positive climate is a prerequisite for the subsequent meaningful projects/missions we do together

The point is, however, that the mobilisation of the science communities will require many rounds of accumulative experimentation, and it will not happen if schools and teachers are not given the needed space to create such experimentation.

The mobilisation of science communities for innovative science learning is depending of the resources of schools and teachers to create and drive the experimentations.

All this is closely related to how innovation in education is depending on schools, teachers and students' motivation.

As another teacher tells us: Schools need to set themselves a goal, find the potential partners, contact them, arrange a meeting, clearly present their needs, ask for support and take advantage of this support by completing the tasks set and presenting the results to the community partners, acknowledging their contribution. In our community sessions we contacted the young mayor, the representatives in the city council, parents who are doctors, former students who were willing to support our missions...

Families are encouraged to become real partners in school life and activities, says the Commission.

One powerful way to engage young students in science in society is to include families in young people's real-life science learning in their everyday life context. Families, especially parents, have a crucial role in influencing students' engagement in science learning. They serve as role models related to the relevance of science in their own professional careers, as well as work as zealous facilitators of students' science learning at home.

According to research, home-school collaboration (HSC) has shown to enhance learning motivation and to promote cultural and educational interactions among the stakeholders.

Furthermore, innovative didactical approaches such as open science schooling that reveal the relevance of science learning in everyday life provides a source of motivation for learners.

This combination of HSC and innovative approaches to science learning such as open science schooling can become a powerful strategy to re-engage the youth in STEAM learning. Families can get involved into open science schooling by

developing STEAM rich environments at home. Families can also promote STEAM related identities among their members, stressing the value of science for society development, for instance.

Finally, families can have a powerful impact on youth science learning by participating directly in STEAM activities with students, as Family Based project promotes.

One of the main goals of the project was to support teachers by building their capacities and skills to deploy innovative science learning opportunities for students alongside family members and their local communities and to engage students and their families in science in the local and virtual communities.

How did the project achieve this objective? by focusing on:

- encouraging families to become partners in school life and activities through active participation
- co-creating 'science everywhere' activities alongside teachers, students and families to support responsible science education
- supporting the deployment of immersive Joint Science Missions involving the community as a whole so that schools become agents of community well-being

However, the project experience tells us that we have to be careful, because families can also act as demotivators of science learning when they do not value STEAM domains, or do not have the repertoire and self-confidence to support it - even if they attribute great value to help their children at science learning. So, be careful not to trespass the line.

As we can see in some answers:

The students like the parents' involvement so long as it doesn't become overly strict, because that would hinder their motivational progress in lessons.

Teenagers do not want their parents to be involved, maybe younger students would be happy to work together with their families.

The students tend to think non-materialistically, so as long as their parents are simply remotely involved, but don't get mixed up in their science missions too much, they are more than glad to welcome them. This means they don't want their parents to get over-involved

We should think about it...

PART 4- THE MISSIONS

Science missions and the power of the epics

TEACHERS

As a project coordinator it was important to be clear about the meaning of the terms – one cannot interpret freely unless they are expected to play with the words – in this sense ‘mission’ was defined in the project as a series of activities meant to make a difference to the community by following the prescribed steps in the Mario presentation (very useful). Also, a mission was expected to form alliances – partnerships – with institutions that are more knowledgeable, influential, powerful, etc. capable of supporting our efforts to achieve the goals we have set ourselves. In addition, these out-of-school partners were also co-creators because they facilitated the design of the missions.

Students defined science missions as "tasks that were meant to raise awareness on important science topics such as global warming, food/water droughts and epidemiology through the lens of open science schooling".

The students have made significant contributions to raising awareness on the topics they discussed.

Involvement was good and beyond 70 percent however it can be always better. Students did their best while struggling with exams and university preparations. They understand that science is not always hard to understand.

Students liked the missions in the community because they challenged them to think, an also because they felt they were doing something useful (unlike the science at home missions where they could not always see the meaning except family time/fun family time together)

Local University support can be explored for future projects. Students can be mobilised for specific experimental activities.

Education institutions should be encouraged to become more entrepreneurial in their wider approach, to ensure that they develop and live a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation through their missions, leadership, stakeholder engagement, curricula and learning outcomes.

European Commission, "Entrepreneurship 2020 Action plan"

This part is devoted to the epics and the power of the epic dimension when creating deep and sustainable interest among teenagers in research, science and, innovation.

And the reader might ask, why talk about "epics" in connection with creating interest in science and innovation among secondary school students?

Because we know from several Commission science education innovation studies and guidelines and recent critical science learning research that to make attractive science and science learning to 21st-century students, science should recover and rediscover the links to narrative and try to communicate the learning in narrative forms.

These links to narrative forms includes for example: adventure, science fiction, exploration, detective work, curiosity, and the ability to take action in such narrative worlds: **narrative and epic agency**.

The term indicates that young students are only likely to be re-engaged in science learning and a life in science to the extent that they can engage deeply in science topics of their interest, follow and explore such science activities across longer periods – and use narrative communication and story-telling to express what they experience and learn.

It also indicates that they need the narrative forms and the epic (immersive) experience to be able to act in the community and to learn through this capacity to agency.

The power of epics

"Epics" is about novels, movies, and all sorts of narratives; and in particular we identify "epics" with great narratives like Ulysses. This "narrative of narratives" takes the hero through all sorts of challenges on a long and complicated journey a bit like the project students' science missions...

The most important narrative in the students' life might, however, be their own identity.

Their identity is a complex narrative defining who they are, what they stand for and what their missions and science missions in life might be.

Important to highlight that in this context the basic structures of this "identity narrative" are created in the teenage years and in secondary school.

In these years their basic narrative is created, also defining them as learners: what they like, what they don't like, what they are good at and not good at.

Some students identify with language, others with science.

What they like and how they like to learn becomes an important part of their identity, of their “identity narrative” and even of their “gender identity narrative”.

So, the teenage years are the most important years for students to get new ways of learning “under their skin”, as such new ways will link to their identity formation. This is the epic dimension...

Therefore, we use the term “epic” to designate these deeper levels of identity, of learning and of ways of learning.

And how can activities have a deep impact on the students:

- the new and innovative learning activities must take place at “epic” level, very different from the traditional Tayloristic organisation of the curriculum
- the new and innovative learning activities must link to and integrate into the creation of their identity, their personality and their life story

What we are saying is that the new learning activities – creating interest in and capacity to innovate – must have **epic quality** to have a serious and lasting impact on the young learners, their identity formation and their life prospects.

And what does epic quality mean here?

Well, it definitely means that punctual, superficial, entertainment-based activities will not work.

Let us list some of the most important “epic quality criteria” for open science schooling strategies and **missions** aiming to create innovation interest among young students by having a deep impact:

OWNERSHIP

The students must own the innovation initiatives, not just follow an initiative from the side-line.

The ownership creates strong personal linking to the science missions and to the learning.

IMPORTANT

The science missions must be important to the community and to the driving students at the same time.

The fact that the science mission is important to the community will ensure motivation to collaborate along many stakeholders and players.

CHALLENGING

The undertaken science mission must be challenging to the students as well as to the collaborating community.

To the extent possible the “epic quality” is increased through the involvement of many fields and forms of knowledge.

DURATION

Logically short duration contradicts “epic”: to have epic quality the science mission needs a certain duration, like any classic narrative.

It must be possible to work through *beginning-middle-ending* scenarios, consisting in many steps, levels or chapters.

Sufficient duration is for example not 6 days but rather 6 months, or not 3 weeks but rather 12 months.

FULL CIRCLE

To the extent possible the students should be involved in the entire life circle of the science mission: such as for example idea, negotiation, planning, resource creation and implementation.

Remember that changing from one school year to another and shifting the school level does not mean that a team cannot continue its engagement in powerful innovation missions.

COLLABORATION

The epic quality of the science mission must include considerable collaboration with as many and as different stakeholders and players as possible.

Dialogues, negotiation, communication and reporting are key narrative elements.

STORY-TELLING

The full epic quality of science missions is supported by systematic and creative story-telling: the students must tell the stories as lively as possible to give their activities meaning, depth and perspective – and to be able to share them with other students.

The innovation missions should be experienced by the students as adventure, exciting journeys – and as their own Ulysses.

SUSTAINABLE

Epic quality is also ensured by the sustainability, not only of the science missions, but also of the students' involvement.

It is important that the undertaken innovation, to the extent possible, can be continued beyond the formal school system: in the students' free time, through after-school activities and integrated in the next school year.

JOINABLE

The open science schooling approach is also open in another sense: open for other students to join, open to various forms of community participation – and open to all sorts of sharing.

The epic quality is therefore increased through the degree of “openness” in the missions.

BUT, IN PRACTICE, WHAT HAPPENS?

It is not a secret what happens, and as already said, it is not easy for secondary schools and teachers to make the needed space, resources, and room available to move to such student-driven science missions in the middle of increasingly overloaded curricula.

It is, in fact, in most schools almost impossible.

Having said that the aim is nevertheless to make the **impossible possible**.

And doing it by remembering that the European Commission encourages constructive “rule-breaking”. Not crazy rule-breaking, but rule-breaking that creates innovation and new learning cultures through breaking the rules of slowly changing systems.

PART 5 - POLICY SUPPORT RECOMMENDATIONS

What messages to send to educational policy-makers?

TEACHERS

*Create the legal basis (integrate such activities in the school curricula).
Erasmus+ projects, good practices and success stories should be promoted in attractive ways to wider audiences.*

Local authorities should endorse scientific engagement either through various stipends or status boosts such as columns in their newsletters and media posts honoring the students who have contributed the most. National authorities could honor them further, either through presidential meetings, sponsorships or status boosts through national coverage in the media. In ERASMUS+ projects, only local authorities could be included, because national authorities can be hard to get a hold of in these trying times of epidemic.

For encouragement they could help for advertisement of the project in the city and increase the capacity and the effect of the project.

STUDENTS

Students like the idea that they could be sponsored by authorities to perform their scientific activities. It would serve as a high form of motivation for them to carry out

massive-scale scientific missions and raise awareness, which is a net positive for the community. It would be a healthy addition to the ERASMUS+ projects.

It has to start with the education system let's imagine you have a kid starting to first grade: this kid has nothing on their mind. They don't know life, nature, science, sky shortly everything they don't know anything. So, if you want to have an interest on science firstly you have to let them play and make some easy and unharmed experiments with that experiment the kid will have confidence and start to have a better view of the science

Government organisations such as ministry of agriculture and forestry may give technical support and provide material for scientific missions.

Schools should develop sustainable and systematic partnerships with businesses, social enterprises and NGOs rather than ad hoc links.

Create 'open door' policies in schools to make them accessible to their local communities; and enabling them to draw on the skills and talents of local people.

Let us conclude this small policy paper by providing some recommendations for educational policy-making and some ideas for the schools willing to change their directions

The recommendations at the same time show and summarize thoughts and messages from the partners.

SCHOOL'S SELF-GOVERNANCE

Policy-making should support open science schooling as the adequate learning didactics of the globalised world – instead of restricting and narrowing the room to move for schools and teachers.

Open room to move should be integrated in all educational planning and curricula.

STRONG STRATEGIC FOCUS ON TEACHER EDUCATIONS

Policy-making should focus strongly on innovation in teacher education, in particular on initial teacher education.

The young generations of teachers are not able to manage the new open schooling and entrepreneurial approaches and the Commission's educational innovation.

Dramatic changes are needed across all teacher educations, including much more practical collaboration with schools and communities.

STRONG NATIONAL COMMITMENT

Policy-making should at national level take seriously the Commission's strategic educational innovation and support the implementation of the innovation instead of undermine it.

LOCAL ENGAGEMENT

Policy-making should ensure much more local engagement from local governments.

Local governments have important roles to play in the field of open schools and cross-sector collaboration – for example supporting the creation of local ecosystems of innovation and entrepreneurial learning.

INVOLVE COMMUNITY – OPEN SCIENCE SCHOOLING

All major educational innovation agendas in Europe are based on and depending on cross-sector collaboration and public and private stakeholders' engagement in learning processes.

Policy-making should support schools at all levels to create open science schooling in collaboration with relevant community stakeholders, including from the private sector.

Policy-makers in particular at local and national levels should bear in mind that it is of paramount importance to mobilise the motivation, creativity and dedication of these educational and community players.

BOTTOM-UP INITIATIVES, NO EVOLUTION

If schools are not able to move and the sector players are increasingly focused on their own challenges, the evolution of the educational system towards open science schooling and 21st century didactics will not happen.

The last two decades have clearly demonstrated this beyond reasonable doubt.

Therefore policy-making should support a bottom-up approach in which the innovation increasingly emerges from pioneer schools and teachers.

Local policy-making should support, celebrate and reward pioneer schools and teachers.

COMMISSION EVALUATION AND CRITIQUE OF NATIONAL EDUCATIONAL POLICY

The Commission should take action to evaluate and criticise national educational policy and make an effort to ensure that Commission educational innovation is followed up at national level.

How can schools get help and support?

Let's imagine we are a secondary school in Italy...

The school has been working with the Family Based material, with the guidance and with the available practical examples.

The school has benefitted from this material. However, the school and in particular a group of teachers would still like to receive some kind of support and help from resources with practical experience in open science schooling to create innovation interest and capacity.

Many schools might be in the same situation: the Family Based material is inspiring and powerful, but...

What kind of questions can we imagine we would ask being the secondary school in Italy?

Probably very many, but let us try to list some of the most important and typical ones:

- how to start the open science schooling activities; what steps to take?
 - how to select the students, and at what age?
 - how could we make the needed room to move in our quite overcrowded curriculum?
 - we should also talk to the parents, right?
 - how can we explain our open science schooling activities to people and institutions in the community? What if they do not understand or do not wish to engage?
 - should we ask permission to the school authorities?
 - how could the extra work be funded; the school is not rich...
 - how to prepare the teachers who will support the students?
 - what kind of subjects should be involved?
 - what about the other teachers that might be affected by the activities?
 - how to guide the students in their science missions' activities? What kind of innovation challenges should they look for?
 - how can we demonstrate that relevant learning is taking place through the open science schooling activities?
 - how to evaluate or assess what the student are learning in these activities?
 - how long time per week for example should the students use? Will they need to work after-school?
- Etc. Etc.

The Italian school and the teachers' team are aware that some answers can be found in the Family Based material. However, their concern is much more: how can we get support along the activities? How can we know if we are doing well or not so well, and if we should change direction?

So, as a school in Italy we are looking for **process support**.

The need for such process support or peer support is quite understandable and justified. In particular if it is the first time the school engages in such experimentation.

Let's make clear that such support does not come easily: in very few countries and regions in Europe such support is available. Typically, the school will have to find its own way.

From where can a school get such support? And what sort of support is possible?

There are different kinds of support, such as:

LOCAL

Local support is difficult to obtain.

In some cases, the municipality is in favour of new learning activities and new opportunities for young people in the community, but that does not mean that they can provide support.

In other cases, science community resources might wish to engage and support, as open science schooling for innovation interest is linked to creating competences and science reengagement on students.

But again: interest does not mean capacity to support.

NATIONAL

If the school is lucky, they might be able to identify higher educations or research and science innovation institutions working with innovation in education and perhaps even with open schooling.

Such institutions might be interested in collaborating with a school that wishes to engage in practical experimentation.

In some cases, national educational authorities make available various forms of funding for pilot projects or different kinds of educational innovation.

The Italian school might try to organise some support through these channels, or identify national research projects that might be interested in collaborating with the school.

If schools have strong school networks, they might try to organise a group of schools that might be able to put some pressure on the national educational authorities.

EUROPEAN

It is always difficult to get support and help for pioneer educational projects.

In particular if the school is among the first schools in the region to engage in such experimentation.

Many schools in Europe therefore end up concluding that the most efficient way to get support and help is through European resources. Strange as it may sound, it is true for many schools.

In our context this means two forms of support and help:

1. support and help through participating in European Erasmus+ projects (like Family Based)
2. support and help from the Family Based project itself

Let's take a closer look at these opportunities:

ERASMUS+ PROJECTS

Any secondary school in Europe can join school partnerships and apply for funding in the Erasmus+ programme.

Of course, this would provide the needed support and help and engage the school in a partnership working towards the same goals.

In this way the school would also be able to finance its experimentation, at least for a 2 years period.

At least in principle because it is not easy to find such partnerships, to write applications and to get the applications granted!

In this case the school and the teacher team should as a first step focus on creating a network of schools in Europe or identifying and joining such networks.

Some help might be obtained from the National Erasmus+ Agencies or through contacts to other schools in Europe, such as the schools and partners in the Family Based project.

It is a lot of work, but it is also the most solid way to start working with open science schooling for innovation interest and to get support and help from qualified and dedicated peers.

THE FAMILY BASED PROJECT SUPPORT

The project is terminated. What remains is the inspirational material available on the project [website](#).

This does not mean that schools cannot establish contact with the project and with the different partners.

Schools and teachers interested in going deeper into how open science schooling strategies can create innovation interest and capacity among young students, perhaps in the form of Erasmus+ projects, are welcome to contact the Family Based resources:

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EXTRA CHAPTER

Key parameters to assess the capacity of innovative learning settings

This chapter is a small contribution and consists of a number of parameters about the capacity of innovative learning settings.

The parameters might be unfolded in further workshops and projects, aiming to find out how to qualify didactic choices in formal and non-formal learning settings, and they might be expanded by other relevant didactics.

KEY INNOVATIVE LEARNING PARAMETERS

General didactic organizing capacity

Learning to learn capacity

Learning motivation

Collaborative skills

Productive, not consuming

Extensive use of Digital (Information and communication)

Extensive use of creative media for production

Linking to community

Capacity to support the new generation of non-academic young learners

INNOVATIVE LEARNING DIDACTICS

Science mission-based learning

Collaborative learning

Problem based learning

Game based learning

Digital supported e-learning

Digital supported classroom learning

The Family Based project has ended, but we can still help...